

Legal metadata standards

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Abstract

Deliverable D3.6.2 (Clusters of agrosystems data in accordance with relevant legal categories) revealed significant differences in licensing practices, access restrictions, data protection considerations and regulatory obligations among FAIRagro's Research Data Infrastructures (RDIs). Deliverable D3.6.3 builds on this by addressing the need to represent the legal properties of agrosystem data in a uniform, machine-readable standard that supports FAIR data principles and integrates consistently across the heterogeneous RDIs. Three main application areas emerged from the analysis, each with distinct requirements for metadata standardisation: Licences, which express the rights and obligations of reuse; data access, which describes access conditions or restrictions; and regulatory requirements, which document obligations arising from legal frameworks such as the Nagoya Protocol.

This document represents Version 1 (22 December 2025) and should be regarded as a living document, subject to ongoing refinement and updates, especially those resulting from the planned workshop "Legal Metadata in FDOs and Infrastructures of Plant Sciences".

Application: Licenses

FAIRagro's Deliverable D3.6.2 (Clusters of agrosystems data in accordance with relevant legal categories) [1] identified the current licence usage across the agrosystems Research Data Infrastructures (RDIs), demonstrating that licences from the Creative Commons (CC) family are predominantly employed. The following licences were reported: OpenAgrar: CC0, CC-BY; BonaRes: CC-BY; Edaphobase: CC-BY-NC (adapted); E!DAL: CC0, CC-BY.

On the basis of these findings, the FAIRagro licensing framework is designed to rely primarily on licences from the Creative Commons family, or on licensing models that adhere to CC principles. Among these, CC0, CC-BY, and CC-BY-NC are anticipated to remain the most frequently used licences, reflecting established practice within the RDIs.

Licensing information is applied at the dataset level and will be embedded within Schema.org metadata to ensure transparent, standardised, and machine-readable declarations of reuse conditions. While a legal distinction exists between CC0 and the public domain, this difference is not considered practically relevant from the perspective of end users. Although Creative Commons licences cannot be legally assigned to research datasets in all cases, RDIs may nevertheless specify them as preferred licensing options, which should be taken into account in accordance with Good Scientific Practice.

Where datasets require specialised licensing terms not represented within existing ontologies, these may be expressed using ODRL (Open Digital Rights Language) [2]. RDIs will be supported in defining such licences through the use of the ODRL Builder tool [3].

Licensing information integrated into Schema.org metadata can be presented in the FAIRagro DataHub through the use of standardised tags and familiar licence logos, thereby enhancing transparency and user accessibility.

Application: Data Access

Embedding in Metadata

Another essential component of the overall metadata framework constitutes the data access. In order to ensure transparent, interoperable, and machine-actionable descriptions of access conditions, FAIRagro adopts the Open Digital Rights Language as the primary mechanism for encoding access policies.

Use cases and their Implementation in ODRL

Work is ongoing to define suitable use cases and to determine whether ODRL statements should be provided as separate files or embedded directly as ODRL objects within the metadata records. This approach is aligned with the principles and structures of FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs), such as ARCs and RO-Crates.

The following representative access scenarios can be modelled using ODRL:

No Restriction

```
"_comment"      : "No restrictions",
"@type"         : "odrl:Rule",
"@id"           : "https://fairagro.net/legalMetadata/OpenAccess",
"odrl:permission": {
  "odrl:action": "odrl:read"
}
```

Registration/Email required

```
"_comment"      : "General restriction of the RDI that only registered
users receive the data",
"@type"         : "odrl:Rule",
"@id"           : "https://fairagro.net/legalMetadata/RegisterRequired",
"odrl:assignee" : {
  "@type": "foaf:OnlineAccount"
}
```

Access upon Request

```
"_comment"      : "Restriction of this data set that data is only
accessible upon request",
"@type"         : "odrl:Rule",
"@id"           : "https://fairagro.net/legalMetadata/DataOnRequest",
"odrl:prohibition": {
  "odrl:action": "odrl:read"
}
```

Representation for the User

In order to ensure an accessible presentation in the FAIRagro Search Hub, it is necessary that each policy is associated with a human-readable representation. In the case of the aforementioned common scenarios, predefined data access statements could be implemented. In cases where no standard policy is applicable, the ODRL Builder can be utilised to generate a custom policy, accompanied by summaries in both German and English.

Actionable Policies

For the implementation, several levels of actionable access policies are distinguished:

Variant 1: Minimal actionable approach

The metadata provide a link to the respective Research Data Infrastructure, where users must independently complete the necessary access procedures.

Variant 2: Identity-enabled approach

Similar to variant 1, but with authentication and authorization supported by the FAIRagro Keycloak service. This enables user identities to be seamlessly transferred to the RDI, with the access process being carried out there. This approach is considered to be applicable to infrastructures such as BonaRes and Edaphobase.

Variant 3: System-mediated access request (planned)

In this model, FAIRagro holds the direct link to restricted data but does not expose it. Users submit access requests through the FAIRagro system, and authorized RDI personnel grant access via a dedicated interface. The implementation of this variant is deferred until a specific use case is identified.

Application: Regulatory Requirements

A further important application area concerns regulatory requirements arising from international agreements or sector-specific legal frameworks, which often impose specific documentation and reporting obligations. These obligations can be (partially) fulfilled through the implementation of structured metadata, thereby ensuring that legally relevant information is provided in a machine-readable and consistent form. Of particular significance is the Nagoya Protocol, which establishes the framework for the utilisation of genetic resources and the compliance with access and benefit-sharing requirements. For example, the metadata may include information on the origin of the resource, the permits obtained, and obligations arising from Material Transfer Agreements. Further, the International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture ("Plant Treaty") may also introduce documentation requirements, for instance by indicating whether material was provided under a Standard Material Transfer Agreement. In the context of these regulatory frameworks, it may be necessary to define harmonised metadata fields ensuring both transparency and the traceability of the legal conditions.

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References

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